

IndraStra™

**MEDIA
KIT
2019**

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MEDIA KIT 2019

PROFILE

IndraStra Global is a "Strategic Analysis & Information Services Provider", primarily focused on data-driven academic research which includes assessment and interpretation, based on "O.O.D.A." (Observation - Orientation - Decision - Action) Framework. We engage ourselves in studying the short-term and long-term impacts of such information on public advocacy, media exposure, and societal influence over multiple broadcasting platforms.

SERVICES

- Opinions & Insights
- News Syndication
- Press Releases
- Academic Syndication
- Books/eBooks Publishing

AFFILIATES

- Google News/Google Books
- Microsoft Bing News (US)
- NewsNow (UK)
- Facebook News (Registered)
- Flipboard and Newstex (US)

MEDIA REACH

50k+ Followers

1.2k+ Followers

200+ Followers

YOY% UNIQUE VISIT/MONTH (AVERAGE) SOURCE: GOOGLE ANALYTICS

ALEXA RANK
1.5 million (approx.)

SIMILAR WEB RANK
1.6 million (approx.)

DOMAIN AUTHORITY
49

